

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation. The article addresses one of the urgent problems - transformation of higher education in the conditions of digitalization. The article discusses the main directions of digital transformation, which radically changes the economy, education and lifestyle in general. It's been shown that digital technologies are necessary for the educational process but not sufficient for increasing the effectiveness of academic work.

Keywords: digital technologies, education system, digital transformation, educational work, students, training, teacher, Internet, higher education, digitalization, digital economy, online education.

Digital technologies are rapidly spreading and evolving. This creates unlimited access to digital tools, materials and services. Students and teachers can gain unprecedented control over their data and shared access. During their quality education and the formation of their interest in learning, the possibility of self-control and checking each other will expand. As you can see, there are many competitive resources for students and teachers: digital learning resources, educational programs, online courses and various online services and components designed to provide a modern learning process.

According to a study conducted by Oxford scientists Karl Frey and Michael Osborne, the professions of teachers, coaches and managers will not face a crisis as a result of robotization. Digitization of education cannot be denied, it is only necessary to adapt to it, master new tools and acquire new skills. According to the forecast of Synergy University, in a few years there will be an increase in the demand for new professions in the market, such as the developer of educational trajectories, Tudor or architect of the virtual world. The penetration of digital technologies (RT) into all spheres of life requires new quality education for graduates. Digitization affects not only the content of education, but also its organization. These processes have different effects on the composition of professors and teachers in universities. Necessary competences are often created outside educational institutions, because educational programs often do not correspond to the dynamics of

technology development. The teacher turns from a provider of knowledge and skills into a navigator who helps in managing knowledge bases. The professor-teacher is evaluated not based on his scientific activity, but on the basis of how well he/she knows science. Pedagogical work acquires a new character.[7]

Research by scientists Kramarenko N.S., Kvashin A.Yu., Karakozov S.D., Uvarov A.Yu., Akimova O.B. showed that digital transformation has a late effect on educational organizations due to limited resources and insufficient digital literacy of teachers. The digital revolution brings with it tools to solve the problems we face. A person who skillfully uses digital technologies and tools in his/her work will significantly increase his intellectual work efficiency. There are hundreds of thousands of educational manuals in digital resources available on the Internet, thanks to which students have a real opportunity to study educational materials taking into account their individual characteristics and needs, and it is possible to differentiate whether the educational material has been completed, and each student is obliged to present the given task in full. The main means of creating the content of education in an educational institution should be the requirements for educational results, the standards of educational achievements. It should be paid attention that digital technologies offer many opportunities to improve education, but their integration into the educational process takes a long time and is not a simple idea.

Digital technology equipment in educational organizations does not lead to higher educational results. Wide introduction of digital technologies at all stages of the education system in Uzbekistan and increasing the level of digital knowledge necessary for the modern economy, improving the educational infrastructure, as well as, within the framework of the implementation of the "Five Initiatives" project in all regions of the republic by 2022 is planned to open training centers for digital knowledge[1]. The importance of the electronic library system, which allows remote access, is also great in improving the quality of education. It expands the opportunities of students to continuously improve their professional skills by enabling them to use the library fund and information bases even after completing their studies at the higher educational institution, conference materials of the higher educational institution, graduation-qualification works. It provides opportunities to use the electronic database of scientific and technical data consisting of master's and doctoral

theses and to use the anti-plagiarism system in order to ensure the freshness of future scientific and technical data. These tasks are performed by information resource centers of higher education institutions. The electronic library is one of the great possibilities of the Internet. They are called differently: Electronic library, Virtual library, e-library, e-library, digital library. In Western countries, for example, in the USA, the automation of libraries began in the 60s, and the creation of electronic collections by entering books into computers has been done since 1971. The popularization of the Internet in our country from the end of the 90s to the beginning of the 2000s allows us to create electronic libraries and communicate with the people of our country and the world.[4]

The implementation of the "E-minbar" platform, which allows online monitoring and learning of lectures and practical exercises, seminars, as well as uploading them to voters, will raise the quality of education to a new level. E-minbar is a new technology for explaining lesson materials without being distracted from the topic statement, and is equipped with various information and equipment necessary for the teacher. The sound amplification device ensures that the voice of the teacher and the presented multimedia materials reach the students well. This software platform is convenient for the professor-teacher to organize his work in their virtual office, to get acquainted with the lesson schedule for the current date, the calendar-thematic (calendar-thematic) plan, today's topic and other information related to the lesson. It is also a convenient tool for providing more information on the subject to students during the training.

The use of the "Electronic University" platform is of great importance for the improvement of the preserved traditional education system, for the further strengthening of the existing "transparent educational environment", and for preventing possible abuses in educational activities. Today's unique features of this system are shown in the following:

- this platform allows students of higher education institutions to gain extensive knowledge by improving the quality of education and the professor-provides opportunities for quick and high-quality communication with teachers;
- eliminating territorial barriers, provides students studying in the distance type of education with the same educational opportunities outside the higher education institution;
- excessive spending is prevented. [6]

It should be paid attention that students and employees of the electronic university system must have the skills of timely and effective use of information technologies, finding necessary information from information resources, independent work and analysis. The introduction of the electronic university system, in turn, requires the development of educational and teaching-methodical materials used in the course of education with reprocessing in the field of sciences. At the same time, electronic educational literature, presentation-slides, audio and video-lectures, and electronic tests intended for teaching in interactive methods will be developed and placed on the platform. In 2019-2020, a special innovative project was implemented at the Tashkent State Law University, as a result of which it is planned to expand the opportunities for legal education through the creation of the "Electronic University" platform.[3] The World Bank will allocate 140,000 US dollars as part of the Academic Innovation Fund grant for this project, which won the international competition. As a result of the implementation of the grant project, it is planned to create the most modern and innovative scientific and educational electronic programs. In particular, by creating programs such as "Electronic Research", "Electronic Education", "Electronic Pedagogue", "Electronic Student", "Electronic Library", "Electronic Legal Advocacy" within the framework of the "Electronic University" platform and integrating them into a single global platform, any university resources can be utilized.[5] It is envisaged to use the point easily, without excessive difficulties, to introduce the latest information and communication technologies into the educational process.

In conclusion, when introducing digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process, it is important to implement the following suggestions:

- individualization of educational processes based on digital technologies, development of distance education services, wide implementation of webinar, online, "blended learning", "flipped classroom" technologies;

- to accelerate the creation of national electronic educational resources, to develop the organization of translation of foreign electronic educational resources;

- increasing and encouraging research and development works in the field of digital technologies, improving their organizational mechanisms;

- To improve the quality of education, to expand the activity of foresight centers to conduct innovative research by attracting specialists and experts of the most prestigious international scientific centers.

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